

OpenRiskNet

RISK ASSESSMENT E-INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable Report D1.2

Associated partner program is
established

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OpenRiskNet: Open e-Infrastructure to Support Data Sharing, Knowledge
Integration and *in silico* Analysis and Modelling in Risk Assessment

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www.openrisknet.org

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The background information and the context was updated.	Introduction
Interactions established with stakeholders, online resources available and the status of the associated partner programme. Additional details on the Standard Agreement and the Implementation Challenge supporting the programme.	Programme implementation

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SUMMARY

To ensure the usability of the infrastructure, alignment with the community needs as well as pursuing complete coverage of important tools incorporated into the e-infrastructure and available to Users, OpenRiskNet will work with a continuously expanding network of partners. To make the interaction with the OpenRiskNet consortium, to give feedback and to contribute to the developments and case study work as simple as possible but also give the opportunity to share confidential information, foster collaborative developments between consortium and associated partners and even allow integration of tools as in-kind work, three different ways to associate with the project as a third party are available: 1) testing the infrastructure as a early adopter and give feedback and state requirements via the online surveys (see also updated deliverable report D1.1), 2) become an official associated partner allowing the exchange of confidential information like source code with examples of service integration and 3) applying to the implementation challenge, which will provide additionally to the technical support also financial support for service integration. This updated deliverable report describes these options organised in the Associated Partner Programme.

This programme aims at strengthening the working ties between the OpenRiskNet Consortium members and other organisations within the scientific and technology communities. Any organisation such as a University, institute, consortium, non-governmental organisation (NGO), a small or medium enterprise (SME) or a large commercial company can become an Associate Partner of OpenRiskNet. We expect to have two different types of users: service providers, who would like to integrate their databases and software tools into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure, and early adopters, who will use the infrastructure for their predictive toxicology and risk assessment tasks and as such provide feedback on their experiences and demonstration showcases of the services and functions provided by the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure.

To establish this network, rules for the Associated Partner Programme were defined, formalised, checked by the legal departments of OpenRiskNet partners and finally accepted by the consortium. The programme was then announced and officially launched during the OpenTox Euro 2017 conference held in Basel, 21-23 November 2017, and co-organised by the OpenRiskNet project. Introduction and demonstration virtual meeting were organised throughout September and October 2018, the infrastructure and the associated partner programme was disseminated at different conferences and workshops throughout 2018 and the website was updated to further promote the programme. All these activities will also be continued in 2019. Details on the Associated Partner Programme are also available at: <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/>.

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of OpenRiskNet is to develop an open e-Infrastructure providing resources and services designed, optimised and combined into workflows to satisfy the requirements of a variety of communities requiring predictive toxicology and risk assessment, including chemicals, cosmetic ingredients, therapeutic agents and nanomaterials. To achieve this goal and guarantee that the infrastructure is fit for purpose, OpenRiskNet beneficiaries will work with a network of partners, organised within the Associated Partners Programme. The partners can decide on the level they want to get involved in the activities of the project, including testing of the provided services, provide additional services and/or contribute to the definition and execution of the case studies.

The main levels ordered from the least to the most involvement are:

- 1) Registering as a user of the reference virtual research environments operated by the OpenRiskNet project providing feedback via filling out the requirement surveys, reporting bug via the support infrastructure and/or following discussions on the case studies on a voluntary basis;
- 2) Becoming an official associated partner by signing a partner agreement with the OpenRiskNet consortium, which allows the partner to participate in the OpenRiskNet consortium meetings, to get access to confidential material like source code with implementation examples and, in this way, to directly be involved in shaping the infrastructure specifications;
- 3) Applying to the implementation challenge, which supports the implementation of services of the associated partners technically and financially.

The associate partner programme has been formalised, under which entities can now associate themselves with OpenRiskNet. Under this programme, the associate partners can actively participate in the design of the e-infrastructure and get access to development versions that are not yet released to the wider community. Additionally, the involvement of external service providers will be fostered by the Implementation Challenge, in which specific tools will be selected and their integration into the e-infrastructure will be technically and financially supported by OpenRiskNet. This integration of databases and tools from consortium members and through the associated partner programme will make a wide range of technologies, research results and data available to all stakeholders. Finally, cooperation with other infrastructure projects and technology companies and providers are established under this programme to get support for the integration of the state-of-the-art approaches and tools developed by these technology partners into the OpenRiskNet platform and to promote the uptake of OpenRiskNet concepts in other projects and consortia.

The main benefits envisaged for associated partners include:

- For **service providers**:
 - greater visibility of their tools by being listed in the OpenRiskNet discovery service;
 - access to infinite additional features by combining with other tools;
 - support for emerging techniques such as API development and containerization/deployment.
- For **early adopters**:

- easy access to an increasing number of tools using user-preferred access routes (web, workflow tools like knime, scripts) without the need to manually download data or convert files when moving from one tool to another;
- harmonised access for comparison of different approaches.
- For **technology partners**:
 - getting feedback on the usability of their services and tools and seeing them in a real-world application
 - being able to use the success story for marketing.

All associated partners will also have the opportunity to apply for support (technical and potentially financial) with integration via the Implementation Challenges (see details below).

PROGRAMME IMPLEMENTATION

To ensure strong, fruitful and meaningful interactions between different parties, an associated partner programme was established and officially launched¹ at the [OpenTox Euro 2017 conference](#), which took place in Basel on 21-23 November 2017 and was co-organised by OpenRiskNet (and other EU-funded projects ACEnano, EU-ToxRisk and in3). From now on, associated partners will be granted an integration support access and will have the opportunity to actively contribute to shaping the OpenRiskNet infrastructure. This ranges from using the infrastructure and giving feedback via the requirement survey and support desk, participating in meeting as official associated partner and providing additional tools funded by the implementation challenge. These different levels will be described in more detail below.

Registered users of the reference environments, requirements survey and support desk

All OpenRiskNet-compliant services are made available on cloud infrastructures (the first instance is operated at the Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing Science Cloud and a second one will be deployed to the Birmingham Environment for Academic Research (BEAR) at the University of Birmingham with a guarantee to be in operation for the next 5 years) and are used to attract developers and end users to the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure. Additionally, they are meant as an unbureaucratic way to open collaborations with relevant parties and projects to foster the adoption of the OpenRiskNet concepts, which can then later be formalised more by an official associated partner status or the implementation challenge.

After the start of the production reference instance operation (March 2018) and the official start of the associated partner programme, multiple virtual introduction and demonstration webinars were provided to interested parties (reaching together approximately 70 people), the infrastructure was presented at different conferences and informational material was produced and distributed (for more information see D3.4 and updated MS1 Detailed plan for the dissemination and exploitation of the project results). This resulted in a significant increase in the number of stakeholders contacting OpenRiskNet consortium partners requesting more information, in the number of users and in the usage of single services and development of workflows combining services to provide answers to users' requests. Due to privacy policies, we only have statistics for the two services, jupyterhub and squonk, which require login via the single-sign-on system of OpenRiskNet with a total of 31 users at the time of this writing. A first practical outcome of the stakeholder involvement is the design of an additional case study on physicochemical characterization of nanoparticles (see also updated D1.1 report). Additional introduction webinars as well as more specific demonstration and training webinars are planned throughout the time of the project to continuously attract more users. These webinars are also recorded and [made available on the OpenRiskNet website](#) so that interested parties can view them at any convenient time if they were not able to attend the webinars directly or if they want to revisit some of the demonstrations.

¹ <https://openrisknet.org/news/2/>

We are inviting any user of the reference instances, participants in the introduction and demonstration webinars and visitors of the OpenRiskNet website to fill in a (version 1), investigating the needs of end users and developers for the knowledge e-infrastructure for risk assessment. Version 1 of the survey was used for the initial requirements analysis leading to the final design concepts of the infrastructure and the development of the first set of case studies (see updated D1.1). Since then, we modified the [survey](#) (version 2) to include more questions asking for feedback on concrete implementations of the concepts and interest in contributing in the case studies with expertise, data or tools. Responses to the surveys represents an excellent starting point to include requirements of the stakeholders and follow-up with more specific discussions on how to best support them with, on one hand, scientific questions like identification, selection and installation of relevant data sources and tools as well as combining these into workflows with applying different tools and, on the other hand, technical question on deployment and running of the infrastructure and getting their tools integrated into the OpenRiskNet ecosystem.

Official associated partner status

Following the dissemination of the infrastructure and first testing of services by independent users, various parties have expressed an interest in becoming associated partners of the OpenRiskNet project and communication lines and contacts were established in order to start the negotiations. A list of potential associated partners was started, including details on the contact points from both sides. To provide the legal framework, detailed Associated Partner Guidelines and standard Associated Partner Agreements, described in more detail below, were prepared and were communicated to the interested parties. The latter is needed for service providers and early adopters in order to be able to bilaterally share information including also confidential data, and to invite partners to project-internal meetings and, in this way, include the associated partners directly in the design process of OpenRiskNet. To speed up the negotiation process, the standard agreements can be signed by the OpenRiskNet coordinator on behalf of the consortium. More specific agreements will also be possible for individual partners but these need to be agreed on by all OpenRiskNet partners individually.

At the time of this writing (November 2018), five parties have joined the OpenRiskNet programme as official partners.

This includes Red Hat and the Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing Science Cloud as technology partners as well as the Diamond Light Source, University of Oxford and the research group of Andrew Nelson (Coordinator of H2020 HISENTS project) from the University of Leeds as early adopters. Highlights of the interactions with these partners are the hosting of the reference instance (SSC), faster development cycles enabled by individual support from the technology partner (Red Hat) and the deployment of a virtual research infrastructure inside the premises of an associated partner (Diamond), with that VRE being used for hosting their own production systems as well as OpenRisknet partner applications.

Negotiations with additional partners are ongoing and especially the number of service providers will be increase in the near future related to the first selection round of the Implementation Challenge. The information on the existing and new partners is made publicly available on the [OpenRiskNet Associated Partner Programme website](#) as soon as

the negotiations have been successfully completed and the partner agrees to the publication (following the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)).

Programme guideline to obtain the official associated partner status

Associated Partner Programme Guideline, version 1.1

Guidelines of the OpenRiskNet Associated Partner Programme

The OpenRiskNet project aims to develop an e-infrastructure providing data sources and software tools as services for predictive toxicology and risk assessment in a harmonised and interoperable way. To ensure the usability of the infrastructure, alignment with the community needs, and pursuit of complete coverage of important tools, OpenRiskNet works with a network of partners, organised into the Associated Partners Programme.

What is in there for me?

We envision two types of associate partners: 1) partners willing to include their services into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure and 2) individual partners or partner projects interested in using the infrastructure to support their daily work in predictive toxicology and risk assessment. Non-exclusive lists of benefits for these groups are:

Service providers: greater visibility of their tools by being listed in the OpenRiskNet discovery service, infinite additional features by combining with other tools, support for emerging techniques like API development and containerization/deployment.

Early adopters: easy access to an increasing number of tools using user-preferred access routes (e.g., web, workflow tools like knime, scripts) without the need to manually download data and convert files when moving from one tool to another, harmonised access for comparison of different approaches.

Who can become an Associate Partner of OpenRiskNet?

The Associated Partner Program aims at strengthening the working ties between the OpenRiskNet Consortium members and other organisations within the scientific community. An organisation such as a university, institute, consortium, non-governmental organisation (NGO), as well as a small or medium-sized enterprise (SME) or a large commercial company can become an Associate Partner of OpenRiskNet.

How to become an Associate Partner?

An organisation interested in the Associated Partner Program can informally contact the coordinator of OpenRiskNet or any other member of the consortium. Additionally, the OpenRiskNet consortium members will actively search and approach organisations, which have been identified as providers of relevant services. Negotiations will be started between the coordinator and the organisation aiming at signing an Associated Partner Programme Agreement, which will cover the roles and responsibilities of both parties, as well as provide a basis for exchange of information. On acceptance, the partnership will be publicly

communicated and put onto the OpenRiskNet website. In addition to becoming an Associated Partner, the organisation can also apply for the Implementation Challenges of the OpenRiskNet project, which provides financial support in the form of in-kind work to selected organisations. In this challenge, external tools especially in areas of risk assessment not completely covered by the OpenRiskNet consortium will be selected for prioritised integration, which will be supported partially financially and strongly technically by researchers of OpenRiskNet partners. The exact conditions will be negotiated individually with the winners of these challenges.

What are the obligations of an Associated Partner providing services?

The first of the primary aims of the Associated Partner Programme is to extend the number of services available in the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure by integration of data source and software tools provided by the Associated Partners and, in this way, make the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure more attractive to all stakeholders. This integration will include the following steps:

- Development and harmonisation of APIs for accessing the data and tool services
- Service containerisation for easier deployment
- Integration of the tools in workflows for defining standard approaches for predictive toxicology and risk assessment in research and regulatory settings

To achieve these goals, the Associated Partner is responsible for:

- providing interfaces to their services, which can be accessed by other OpenRiskNet services and
- providing a containerised version of their services or all information needed to containerise the service by an OpenRiskNet partner and
- providing information on licensing and access rights to the services.

The OpenRiskNet Consortium is responsible for:

- providing detailed technical documentation on the OpenRiskNet infrastructure and the harmonisation and interoperability communications layer and
- providing access to the OpenRiskNet reference instance of the virtual environment for testing of the functionality and usability of the Associated Partner's tool / service and
- providing premium user and integration support and
- trying to adapt the infrastructure according to any requirements and shortcomings identified by the Associated Partner.

What are the obligations of an Associated Partner as early adopter?

The second primary aim of the Associated Partner programme is to increase the stakeholders involvement in the layouting of the infrastructure by including feedback from early adopters. Associated Partners will be given access to the reference virtual instance and all provided services allowing them to apply these tools for work related to publically-funded projects, case study work of OpenRiskNet and internal projects.

Similar to the task described above for service providers, the OpenRiskNet Consortium is responsible for:

- providing detailed technical and scientific documentation on the OpenRiskNet infrastructure and the harmonisation and interoperability communication layer and
- providing access to the OpenRiskNet reference instance of the virtual environment, OpenRiskNet services and workflows resulting from the case studies for testing of the functionality and usability and
- providing premium user and integration support.

The Associated Partner will:

- provide feedback on the usability and fitness of the e-infrastructure for risk assessment and predictive toxicology applications and
- suggest additional features for the core infrastructure as well as important data sources and services to be included and
- contribute to the case study work by providing alternative approaches or even suggesting additional case studies.

Standard Agreement between associated partners and the OpenRiskNet consortium

For facilitating a faster communication and implementation of the Programme and for simplifying the legal procedure, standard agreements for the Associated Partner Programme were prepared (two variants targeting service providers and early adopters, respectively) with the support of the legal departments of the at that time first two associated partner applicant University of Oxford and Diamond Light Source and were accepted by the OpenRiskNet consortium. Moreover, a paragraph was included in the Consortium Agreement (6.4.6) mentioning that the coordinator is entitled to start negotiations and sign the corresponding standard agreement on behalf of the consortium with third parties, which seek to become a member of the Associated Partner Programme. However, all partners will be informed about these negotiations immediately after the first contact, allowing them to express any objection on the planned partnership.

Technology partnerships are mainly focused on bilateral exchange of experience and support of integration of emerging new technologies. Therefore, they will not be formalised by standard partner agreements. Technology partners can just join by accepting an invitation letter if no confidential information is planned to be exchanged. However, special agreement will be necessary if custom-made solutions will be provided by either the associated partner or OpenRiskNet.

Associated partners supported by the implementation challenge

The Implementation Challenge² was created to select external tools especially in areas of risk assessment not completely covered by the OpenRiskNet consortium to be prioritised for their integration into the e-infrastructure. Third parties can apply for partial financial and strongly technical support by researchers and developers of OpenRiskNet partners. Similar to the internal services, the funds and the technical support will cover the work

² <https://openrisknet.org/associated-partner-programme/implementation-challenge/>

associated with making the service OpenRiskNet compliant. This includes the adoption of the OpenRiskNet API concept including the interoperability layer, generation of the data schemata for in- and output as well as the containerization for deployment.

At the end of the first selection period (31 October 2018), **10 parties have applied to the Implementation Challenge** for financial support of the integration of their services into the OpenRiskNet infrastructure. Following the agreed rules of the challenge, these applications have been **evaluated by the scientific advisory board** (November 2018) and the winners were announced. Two additional selection rounds will follow in **December 2018** and **April 2019**. These winners will then be integrated in the project first as official associated partners to be able to start detailed discussion on the technical developments needed for the integration without being limited by not being able to share confidential information. After these discussions resulted in a clear implementation plan and time table, more specific agreements will be prepared and signed by the associated partner and the consortium partner providing the budget for the in-kind work (Douglas Connect, Maastricht University or University of Birmingham).

CONCLUSIONS

Multiple actions were taken in relation to the Associated Partner programme, including the preparation of standard agreements (documents accepted by the OpenRiskNet consortium) and guidelines with details on the programme. The associated partner programme was then officially launched at the OpenTox Euro 2017 Conference, Basel on 21-23 November 2017. In parallel, introduction and demonstration webinars were given and the project was disseminated at different conferences and meetings to attract interested parties. Based on the feedback of these dissemination events and the personal network of the consortium partners, a list of potential associated partners was prepared and members of the consortium were assigned to contact them individually and continue the discussions to motivate them to become registered users of the reference virtual research environment, join the project as official associated partner or apply to the Implementation Challenge. These activities resulted in a large number of new users, up to now 5 official associated partners and 10 applications to the first round of the Implementation Challenge.

GLOSSARY

The list of terms or abbreviations with the definitions, used in the context of OpenRiskNet project and the e-infrastructure development is available at:

<https://github.com/OpenRiskNet/home/wiki/Glossary>